

A CLINICAL STUDY TO EVALUATE THE COMBINED EFFECT OF VAMANA AND SHAMANANGA SNEHAPANA IN EKAKUSHTA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO PSORIASIS-CASE SERIES

Dr. Purushottam Dasar*¹, Dr. Rajesh Sugar², Dr. Shilpashree³, Dr. Santosh L. Yadahalli⁴

¹Post Graduate Scholar, ²Professor, ³Assistant Professor, ⁴Professor and HOD
Dept. of PG Studies in Panchakarma Taranath Govt. Ayurvedic Medical College and Hospital Ballari, Karnataka.

*Corresponding Author: Dr. Purushottam Dasar

Post Graduate Scholar, Dept. of PG Studies in Panchakarma Taranath Govt. Ayurvedic Medical College and Hospital Ballari, Karnataka. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18429747>

How to cite this Article: Dr. Purushottam Dasar*¹, Dr. Rajesh Sugar², Dr. Shilpashree³, Dr. Santosh L. Yadahalli⁴. (2026). A Clinical Study To Evaluate The Combined Effect Of Vamana and Shamananga Snehapana In Ekakushta With Special Reference To Psoriasis-Case Series. European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 13(2), 223–230. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 05/01/2026

Article Revised on 25/01/2026

Article Published on 01/02/2026

ABSTRACT

Background: Ekakushta is a Tvak Roga mentioned under Kshudra Kushta having symptoms like Aswedana, Mahavastu, Matsya Shakalopama, which resembles Psoriasis, a common chronic inflammatory skin disease characterized by well-demarcated erythematous, raised plaques with silvery white scales. Classical texts recommend Shodhana Chikitsa followed by Shamana Chikitsa for effective management. **Objective:** To assess the combined effect of Vamana Karma with Pancha Kashaya followed by Amrita Ghrita Shamananga Snehapana in Ekakushta (Psoriasis). **Methods:** A clinical study was conducted on 20 patients. Treatment of Deepana Pachana with Shunti Choorna was followed by Snehapana with Murchita Ghrita. Vamana Karma was performed using *Pancha Kashaya* with Madanaphala and Madhu. After Samsarjana Krama, patients received Amrita Ghrita Shamananga Snehapana for 15 days. Outcomes were assessed based on clinical improvement using PASI as objective parameter. **Results:** 20% of patients showed marked improvement, 45% moderate improvement, 20% mild improvement, and 15% no improvement. **Conclusion:** Vamana Karma with Pancha Kashaya followed by Amrita Ghrita Shamananga Snehapana was effective in managing Ekakushta (Psoriasis), indicating choice of intervention by considering lesion site, surface area, and chronicity thus proving the **Urdhva Amashaye Vamana**.

KEYWORDS: Ekakushta, Psoriasis, Vamana Karma, Pancha Kashaya, Shamananga Snehana, Amrita Ghrita PASI.

INTRODUCTION

Skin is the most exposed boundary with the outside world & provides a barrier between the environment & internal organs. Skin diseases are often obvious and visible to others. Those who suffer from them have to cope with both their disease and the negative reaction of others because of the stigma traditionally associated with these types of conditions. Acharya Sushruta opines that Twacha is formed by nourishing factor Ksheera during Shukra- Shonita Sanyoga and it is a seven layered structure. Kushta manifests in the fifth layer called Vedini. One which produces discoloration over body surface/skin is said to be Kushta, it is included under Astamahagada. It affects the Twacha initially, if not treated then spreads to the next Dhatu in later stage. It is a Santarpana Janya Roga, Mainly categorized into two

groups Mahakushta and Kshudra Kushta, but they can be innumerable. Ekakushta^[1] is a type of Kushta Roga mentioned under Kshudra Kushta having symptoms like Aswedana, Mahavastu, Matsya Shakalopama, which resembles Psoriasis^[2], a common chronic inflammatory skin disease characterized by well-demarcated erythematous, raised plaques with silvery white scales. The reported prevalence^[3] of Psoriasis in countries ranges between 0.09% and 11.4% making Psoriasis a serious global problem. Psoriasis causes great physical, emotional and social burden & quality of life in general is often significantly impaired. Ekakushta is a Vata Kapha Pradhana Tridoshaja^[4] Vikara, where Shodhana Chikitsa administered through nearest route is necessary treatment for elimination of vitiated Doshas from the body followed by Shamana Chikitsa for elimination of

remnant Doshas. Vamana Karma with Pancha Kashaya^[5] mentioned in Kushta Roga Chikitsa, which helps to eliminate vitiated Doshas as well does Roga Shamana. Administration of Tridosha Shamaka and Kushtahara

Sneha like Amrita Ghrita^[6] in the form of Shamananga Snehapana help in treating the Vyadhi and to control the Vata dosha after the Shodhana.

Table no. 1: Nidana- Samprapti of Ekakushta.

NIDANA	SAMPRAPTI	POORVAROOPA	ROOPA
Viruddha anna pana, Ati-Drava snigdha guru, sheeta-ushna-langhana Ahara or akramasevana, sheetambu sevana after gharma-shrama-bhaya, ajeeranashana, adhyashana, navanna-dadhi-matsya-tila-lavana masha-mulaka-pishtanna-ksheera guda atisevana, chardi vega dharana, bhojanottara ati Vyayama, bhojanottara ati santapa, diva nidra, panchakarma apachara, guru-dharma vipra, papakarma, mitya vihara, snehapeetaya-vantasya vyayama, gramya-anup-audaka,mamsa, payasa, atyushmabhitapta.	Nidana sevana leads to vatadi dosha prakopa; vitiated doshas undergo tiryagata siradi gamana and cause shithilata of tvacha, rakta, mamsa, and lasika. Through sthana samshraya in tvacha, mandala and vaivarnya manifest and expression as ekakushta.	asveda, vaivarnya, kotha, lomaharsha, kandu, sheegrotpatti - sthirastiti, daha, suptanga/svapa, atishlakshna, kharasparsha, rukshatva, tvak - parushya, asruja - krishnata.	Asvedana, Mahavastu/Mahash raya, Matshyashakala, Krishna, Aruna Varna of Shareera.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted at Taranath Government Ayurvedic Medical College and Hospital, Ballari, with literary data sourced from libraries, journals, periodicals, published works, and online references. Patients diagnosed with Ekakushta were selected from OPD and IPD, while raw drugs were authenticated and trial medicines prepared under expert guidance in the pharmacy section. Data collection followed a structured proforma covering clinical history, examination, and laboratory findings. The research design was an open - labeled, randomized, clinical study with a minimum of 20 patients, selected based on inclusion criteria and treatment was given after obtaining Consent.

DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA

Diagnosed based on classical signs & symptoms of Ekakushta/Psoriasis as mentioned below, Aswedana, Mahavastu, Matsyashakalopama, Kandu, Erythema, Thickness/Induration, Scaling, Candle grease test, Auspitz sign, and Koebners phenomenon.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- Subject presenting with Lakshanas of Ekakushta.

INTERVENTION

Table no. 2: Intervention.

STEPS	TREATMENT	DURATION
PURVA KARMA	Atura siddhata- Counselling and consent taking Deepana -Pachana with Shunti Choorna. Dose: 3grams three times a day, before food Anupana: Sukhoshna Jala.	1-5 days / till Nirama Lakshanas appears.
	Snehapana with Murchita Ghrita in Arohana Krama. Dose: Depending upon Agni and Koshtha. Anupana – Ushnajala.	3 to 7 days
	Vishrama Kala: Sarvanga Abhyanga with Murchita Tila Taila followed by Ushna jala parisheka Sweda.	1 day
PRADHANA KARMA	Vamana Karma with Pancha Kashaya.	1 Day

- Subject presenting with signs and symptoms of Psoriasis.
- Subject of age between 18 to 60 years of either sex.
- Subject fit for Vamana Karma.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- Lactating mother and pregnant women.
- Subject suffering from chronic systemic infectious diseases like TB, HIV, HBsAg etc. and uncontrolled diabetes or hypertension or cardiac diseases.
- Subject suffering from other skin disease like bacterial, fungal Infections etc.

WITHDRAWAL CRITERIA

Patient can withdraw from the trial at any time, for the following reasons or as the case may be

- Health and safety issues
- Personal reasons
- Noncompliance
- Discontinued follow up

PASHCHAT KARMA	Mukha, Pani, and Pada Prakshalana. Dhumapana with Haridra Dhooma Varti. Peyadi Samsarjana Krama.	3 to 7 Days
FOLLOWED BY	Shamananga Snehapana with Amrita Ghrita, 20ml, twice a day, before food.	15 Days
Treatment Duration	Avara-Pravara	24 – 35 Days

DURING VAMANA PROCEDURE

Figure no 1. Showing Procedure of Vamana.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

Assessment was made on the basis of the following subjective and objective parameter before treatment, after treatment and after follow up of one week.

Table no 3: Grading for subjective parameter.

SYMPTOMS	SEVERITY	GRADE
1)ASWEDANA	Normal sweating	Grade 0
	Mild sweating	Grade 1
	Moderate sweating on lesions after exercise	Grade 2
	Mild sweating on lesions after exercise	Grade 3
	No sweating on lesions after exercise	Grade 4
2)KANDU	No itching	Grade 0
	Itches but controllable	Grade 1
	Itches but do not disturb patient’s attention	Grade 2
	Distracting patients sleep	Grade 3
	Intolerance and disturbing physical and social activities	Grade 4
3)MAHAVASTU	No lesion	Grade0
	Lesion up to 5cm	Grade1
	Lesion 5-10 cm	Grade2
	More than 10 cm with multiple lesion	Grade3
	All over the body	Grade4
4)MATHSYASHAKALOPAMA	No scale	Grade0
	Less noticeable	Grade1
	Dry scaly scalp/limbs /trunk	Grade2
	Dry scaly including scalp, extensor aspects of limbs and trunk	Grade3
	All over the body	Grade4

OBJECTIVE PARAMETER

PASI SCORE^[7]

PASI score was assessed before treatment, after treatment and after follow up.

patients had negative family history. Different types of psoriasis, cardinal signs and symptoms like scales, Auspitz sign, candle grease sign and Koebners phenomenon were observed.

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

Out of 20 patients, one patient had acute and 19 patients had chronic history. 4 patients had positive and 16

Table no. 4: Observation.

Criteria	Age			Gender		Site of lesion			
	21-30	31-40	41-50	Male	Female	Head	Upper Extremities	Trunk	Lower extremities
No of patients	10	8	2	18	2	16	14	12	14

Table no. 5: Result of Subjective Parameter.

ASWEDANA			KANDU			MAHA VASTU			MATSYA SHAKALOPAMA		
BT	AT	AF	BT	AT	AF	BT	AT	AF	BT	AT	AF
3	2	2	2	1	1	3	0	0	3	1	3
1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0
1	0	0	3	1	1	2	1	1	0	0	0
1	0	0	2	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1
2	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	0	0
1	0	0	3	1	1	3	1	1	1	0	0
1	0	0	2	0	0	2	1	1	2	1	1
2	1	1	2	0	0	2	1	1	2	1	1
1	0	0	3	3	3	2	1	1	2	1	1
1	0	0	3	1	1	3	1	1	2	1	1
2	1	1	2	1	1	3	2	2	3	1	1
2	1	1	3	2	2	3	2	2	2	1	1
3	1	1	4	3	3	4	3	3	3	2	2
1	1	1	3	1	1	3	3	3	2	0	0
1	1	0	2	1	1	3	3	3	1	1	1
3	2	2	4	2	2	3	2	2	3	2	2
2	1	1	2	1	1	3	2	2	3	1	1
2	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	3	1	1
2	1	1	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1
3	2	2	3	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	1

Table no. 6: Result of Objective Parameter.

OBJECTIVE PARAMETER PASI SCORE		
BT	AT	AF
7.5	1.8	4.3
5.6	0.5	0.8
8.4	2.4	2.4
1.8	0.6	0.4
3.6	2.8	2.8
13	2.5	2.5
4	1.2	1.2
5.2	1.5	0.6
10.4	8.8	9.6
12.4	7.4	9
8.1	3.6	3.6
16.3	10.1	10.1
13.3	8.8	8.8
2.4	0.8	0.8
3.3	3	3
17.5	8	8.8
6	3.5	3.5
4.6	2.9	2.9
1.8	0.9	0.9
3.6	2.6	2.6

Table no. 7: Statistical analysis of Result.

PARAMETER		Mean	Relief rate (%)	Sum of the ranks	Mean of the ranks	SD	Z value	P value	Remarks
ASWEDANA	BT	1.75	60.83%	171	85.5	22.96	-3.723	0.0002	S
	AT	0.8							
	BT	1.75	65.83%	190	95	24.85	-3.823	0.0001	S
	AF	0.75							
KANDU	BT	2.55	56.25%	190	95	24.85	-3.823	0.0001	S
	AT	1.2							
	BT	2.55	56.25%	190	95	24.85	-3.823	0.0001	S
	AF	1.2							
MAHAVASTU	BT	2.45	37.08%	105	52.5	15.93	-3.295	0.0009	S
	AT	1.55							
	BT	2.45	37.08%	105	52.5	15.93	-3.295	0.0009	S
	AF	1.55							
MATSYA SHAKALOPAMA	BT	1.9	49.16%	136	68	19.34	-3.516	0.0004	S
	AT	0.85							
	BT	1.9	45.83%	120	60	17.61	-3.407	0.0006	S
	AF	0.95							
PASI SCORE	BT	7.44	50.94%	210	105	26.79	-3.919	0.00008	S
	AT	3.68							
	BT	7.44	49.17%	210	105	26.79	-3.919	0.00008	S
	AF	3.93							

Table no. 8: Overall effect of treatment.

Overall effect	Result	
	N	%
Marked improvement	4	20%
Moderate improvement	9	45%
Mild improvement	4	20%
No improvement	3	15%
Total	20	100%

Graph no 1. Showing the overall result.

OBJECTIVE PARAMETER PASI SCORE		
BT	AT	AF
7.5	1.8	4.3
5.6	0.5	0.8
8.4	2.4	2.4
1.8	0.6	0.4
3.6	2.8	2.8
13	2.5	2.5
4	1.2	1.2
5.2	1.5	0.6
10.4	8.8	9.6
12.4	7.4	9
8.1	3.6	3.6
16.3	10.1	10.1
13.3	8.8	8.8
2.4	0.8	0.8
3.3	3	3
17.5	8	8.8
6	3.5	3.5
4.6	2.9	2.9
1.8	0.9	0.9
3.6	2.6	2.6

Figure no. 2: Showing the changes in skin.

DISCUSSION

Shunti Choorna used for the Deepana & Pachana , contains chemical like Gingerol, Shogaol, Zingerone, which are Antioxidant, and carminative by which it acts as Amapachaka and Agnideepaka.

Murchita Ghrita used for Snehapana is devoid of Amadosh as it was processed with Triphaladi drugs mentioned in Bhaishajya Ratnavali. It was given in Madhyama Matra, in Kaphakala between 6 To 6.30 AM.

It has Guru, Snigdha, Sukshma etc. properties. It does Utkleshana of vitiated Doshas and softness of Srotas to easy passage of Doshas once Swedana is performed. Murchana contribute to low rancidity, polyphenols, flavonoids, and tannins aiding detoxification and Doshas mobilization.

Murchita Tila Taila used for Abhyanga is devoid of Amadosha and external usage in the form of Abhyanga helps in softening the skin and leasion by which dosha

moves easily towards Koshtha. Due to its properties like Ushna, Sukshma enters dermal cells and causes movement of Doshas towards Koshtha.

The ingredients of Panchakshaya like Madhana phala has Saponins^[8], used for vamaana. These surface-active glycosides irritate the gastric mucosa and stimulate the vomiting center through vagal afferents. Some of the alkaloids in *Randia dumetorum* contribute to central emetic action.

Amrita Ghrita used for Shamananga Snehapana contains Alkaloids like Magnoflorine, Berberine, and Palmatine which are Anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and immune-modulating action.^[9] Diterpenoid lactones like Tinosporin, Tinosporide, Cordifolide, Cordifol acts as antipsoriatic, and antioxidant. Glycosides like Tinocordiside, Tinocordifolioside which acts as Immunomodulatory, hepatoprotective and Steroids like β -sitosterol, Ecdysterone which acts as Anti-inflammatory, keratinocyte growth modulation to heal lesions, control growth, and promote the nourishment. Thus combined action of procedure gives reduction in the symptoms and healing of the condition.

As psoriasis is a disease with relapsing and recurrence, extending the duration of treatment with continuation of Adha shodhana following the urdhva shodhana in Sarva shareera vyapta vyadhi along with Shamana for a month, as mentioned by Acharya sushruta may give the fruitful result with prolonged period of remission as noted in the subsequent follow up of patient.

CONCLUSION

To attain optimum result in case of Ekakushta/psoriasis intervention should be selected and performed based on the site of lesion and size/surface area or chronicity, thus the Vamana followed by Shamananga snehana in lesions of Urdhva amashaya is choice of procedure in scalp psoriasis highlighting the **Urdhva Amashaye Vamana**.^[10]

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I bow down to the sacred feet of god lord Vishnu and lord Gavisiddheshwara, without the blessings of whom the study would not have been completed.

I'm Always grateful for the grace of Lord Dhanwantari, blessings of Pandith Taranath Ji and Dr. M Eshwar Reddy Sir.

The contributions of many people, in their different ways, have made this possible. At the end of my work, I would like to thank all those people who made this work possible and made it an unforgettable experience for me.

I would like to thank my family, especially my wife who supported during my study.

I am thankful to Dr. Shridhar B S Principal, Taranath Government Ayurvedic Medical College & hospital, Ballari for their valuable help and guidance.

I sincerely express my indebtedness and profound gratitude to my respected Guide Dr. Rajesh Sugur, Professor, Department of PG studies in Panchakarma, for their valuable guidance, and encouragement throughout the study.

I sincerely express my indebtedness and profound gratitude to my respected Co-guide Dr. Shilpashree, Assistant Professor, Department of PG studies in Panchakarma, for their valuable guidance and constant support throughout my study.

I owe my deep sense of gratitude to all my beloved teachers, Dr. Rajesh Sugur, Dr. Santosh L Y, Dr. Doddabasayya K, Dr. Shilpashree K and all the faculty of TGAMC for their support and guidance. Dr. Shivalingappa J and Hospital RMO Dr. Kotresh S M for their valuable guidance and constant support throughout the study.

I convey my special thanks to my batchmates for their kind co-operation, suggestions and constant help during my entire course of study.

I convey my thanks to Dr. Ankita Reddy and Miss. Vedavati, Statistician for their help in statistical analysis and interpretation.

I also express my gratitude to all of them including the Author of books, journal, online sources, who have helped me directly or indirectly, with sincere apology for my inability to identify them individually.

REFERENCES

1. Agnivesa, Charaka Samhita, Revised by Charaka & Dridhabala, with the Ayurveda dipika commentary of chakrapanidatta edited by Vaidya Jadavaji Trikamji Acharya, Reprint Edition 2023, Chaukhambha Orientalia Varanasi, Chikitsasthana chapter 7/ 21, 451.
2. alit Kumar Gupta, Paschal D'Souza, Abhay Mani Martin, IADVL's CONCISE TEXTBOOK OF DERMATOLOGY, Second Edition, 2019, Reprint 2022, Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers(P) Ltd, chapter 15, 208.
3. [https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/204417/9/789241565189_eng.pdf;j=](https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/204417/9/789241565189_eng.pdf;j=789241565189_eng.pdf;j=)
4. Agnivesa, Charaka Samhita, Revised by Charaka & Dridhabala, with the Ayurveda dipika commentary of chakrapanidatta edited by Vaidya Jadavaji Trikamji Acharya, Reprint Edition 2023, Chaukhambha Orientalia Varanasi, Nidanasthana chapter 5/ 4, commentary by Chakrapanidatta, 216.
5. PRIYA VRAT SHARMA, CAKRADATTA, A Treatise on Principles and Practices of Ayurvedic

- Medicine, Edition 2022, Chaukhambha Orientalia DELHI. Chapter 50, 389.
6. SARNGADHARACARYA, SARANGADHARA SAMHITA, Translated by Dr. P Himasagara Chandra Murthy, Reprint 2018, CHOWKHAMBHA SANSKRIT SERIES OFFICE VARANASI, MADHYAMAKHANDA, chapter 9, 205.
 7. Chief Editor Sharmila Patil, Assistant Editor Ratnakar Shukla, Window to Psoriasis, Second Edition, 2022, CBS Publishers & Distributors Pvt Ltd New Delhi.
 8. Dr. J. L. N. Sastry & Dr. Tanuja M. Nesari, A text book of Dravyaguna Vijnana, reprint edition 2022, vol 2, chaukhambha orientalia, varanasi.
 9. Dr. J. L. N. Sastry & Dr. Tanuja M. Nesari, A text book of Dravyaguna Vijnana, reprint edition 2022, vol 2, chaukhambha orientalia, varanasi.
 10. Agnivesa, Charaka Samhita, Revised by Charaka & Dridhabala, with the Ayurveda dipika commentary of chakrapanidatta edited by Vaidya Jadavaji Trikamji Acharya, Reprint Edition 2023, Chaukhambha Orientalia Varanasi, Chikitsasthana chapter 7.